

Thiazolidinone Formation on Thin-Layer Chromatoplates

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Most of the reactions achieved in this work were conducted with azomethine compounds containing one or two heterocyclic moieties. The reactions were performed on inert thin-layer chromatoplates under controlled conditions and the products of the reactions were compared with the expected substances on the same chromatogram.

APLICATION of chemical reactions on chromatoplates¹⁻³ was developed to solve several problems particularly in the field of natural products. Of late, we have successfully discussed cyclocondensation reaction of ketene on some new Schiff bases (β -lactam formation) on tlc⁴. The bacteriostatic and fungistatic activities^{5,6} of the substituted thiazolidinones prompted us to follow such cyclocondensation reaction on tlc in order to generalize this technique and to overcome some difficulties encountered earlier.

The reaction is generally carried out by mixing the substances under examination mostly in solution form with the reactants within a small spot at the starting line of a plate of an inert adsorbent such as silica gel. The mixture of reactants is then subjected to the favourable conditions and suitable length of time to simulate, as far as possible, the normal reaction conditions in a flask. At the end of the reaction period a simplified working up may be necessary and is performed within the confines of the spots. The adsorbed layer is treated in the normal manner as a chromatographic medium for

the resolution of the components of the reaction mixture. Thus, development with a suitable solvent system enables the detection of the formed derivative and its comparison with the expected material, spotted at the starting line immediately prior to development. Differentiation of the derivative from the starting material, if any remains, is always possible if the appropriate conditions are used.

Results and Discussion

It appears that the application of the thiazolidinone formation of different heterocyclic imines on an inert chromatographic adsorbent, within the area of spot, can produce results comparable to those obtained in conventional reaction apparatus.

The ir spectra of the substituted thiazolidinones produced showed an absorption band around 1700-1695 cm^{-1} due to C=O group⁷ and the disappearance of the band at 1640-1620 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N of the Schiff base⁷. The m.p.s. are identical with those of the authentic samples and no depression in m.m.p. is observed.

TABLE-1

No. of the Comp.	Starting material (R_f)	Reaction product (R_f)	Solvent system ^a
1	5-Bromothiophenylidene-2-aminobenzthiazole (0.70)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-3-benzthiazolyl)thiazolidin-4-one (0.38)	I
2	5-Bromothiophenylidene-2-amino-6-ethoxybenzthiazole (0.76)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-6-ethoxybenzthiazolyl)thiazolidin-4-one (0.48)	I
3	5-Bromothiophenylidene-2-amino-5-chlorobenzoxazole (0.48)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-5-chlorobenzoxazolyl)thiazolidin-4-one (0.16)	I
4	Thiophenylidene-2-amino-4-tolyl-5-phenylthiazole (0.15)	2-Thienyl-3-(4-tolyl-5-phenyl)thiazolylthiazolidin-4-one (0.50)	I
5	5-Bromothiophene-2-carboxaldehydehydrazone (0.87)	2-(5-Bromothieryl)-3-aminothiazolidin-4-one (0.56)	I
6	Bis-thiophenylideneazomethine (0.73)	Bis-2-(5-Bromothieryl-2'-thienyl)thiazolidin-4-one (0.47)	I
7	5-Bromothiophene-2-carboxaldehyde phenylhydrazone (0.82)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-3-anilino)thiazolidin-4-one (0.54)	I
8	5-Bromothiophenylidene-N-urea (0.49)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-3-N-urea)thiazolidin-4-one (0.39)	I
9	5-Bromothiophenylidene-N-thiourea (0.58)	2-(5-Bromothieryl-3-N-thiourea)thiazolidin-4-one (0.46)	I
10	Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde hydrazone (0.70)	2-Thienyl-3-aminothiazolidin-4-one (0.55)	I
11	Bis-thiophenylidene azomethine (0.72)	Bis-2,2'-thienylthiazolidin-4-one (0.42)	I
12	Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde phenylhydrazone (0.66)	2-Thienyl-3-anilinothiazolidin-4-one (0.39)	I

(Table 1 Contd.)

13	Thiophenylidene-N-urea	(0.28)	(2-Thienyl-3-N-urea)thiazolidin-4-one	(0.13)	II
14	Thiophenylidene-N-thiourea	(0.83)	(2-Thienyl-3-N-thiourea)thiazolidin-4-one	(0.48)	I
15	Bis-(thiophenylideneferrocenylidene)azomethine	(0.91)	Bis-(2-thienyl-2'-ferrocenyl)thiazolidin-4-one	(0.73)	I
16	Bis-[thiophenylidene-N-(Me) ₂ benzylidene]azomethine	(0.66)	Bis-2-thienyl-2'-phenyl-N-dimethylthiazolidin-4-one	(0.80)	I
17	p-Chlorobenzylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylmorpholine	(0.62)	2-p-Chlorophenyl-2-benzensulfanyl-morpholinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.42)	I
18	p-Nitrobenzylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylmorpholine	(0.56)	2-p-Nitrophenyl-2-benzensulfanyl-morpholinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.22)	I
19	Salicylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylmorpholine	(0.54)	2-o-Hydroxy-3-benzensulfanyl-morpholinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.29)	I
20	p-Nitrobenzylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylpiperidine	(0.73)	2-p-nitrophenyl-3-benzensulfanyl-piperidinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.34)	I
21	p-Chlorobenzylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylpiperidine	(0.47)	2-p-Chlorophenyl-3-benzensulfanyl-piperidinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.36)	I
22	Benzylidene-p-aminobenzene-sulphonylpiperidine	(0.64)	2-Phenyl-3-benzensulfanyl-piperidinethiazolidin-4-one	(0.30)	I
23	Isatylidene-3-thiosemicarbazone	(0.56)	Spiro indolino-3,1'-thiazolidine-2,4'-diones	(0.27)	I

* Solvent system ; I=benzene-ethyl acetate 7 : 3 ; II=benzene-ethyl acetate 3 : 7.

Formation of most of the thiazolidinone proceeds smoothly on the chromatoplate and the resulting compounds are obtained in good yield. In some cases traces of the starting material remain unreacted.

The reactions carried out are formation of 2-substituted thienylthiazolidin-4-ones (1-16)⁸, 2-substituted sulfanylthiazolidin-4-ones (17-22)⁹ and spiro indolino-3,2'-thiazolidin-2,4'-diones (23)¹⁰.

Experimental

Chromatoplates: These are plastic sheets precoated with 0.25 mm silica gel with fluorescent indicator. The plates were developed by placing them in a closed tank containing iodine.

General method for carrying the reactions on chromatoplates:

The Schiff base under examination in dioxane was applied on a plate at the starting line with dry

benzene and mercaptoacetic acid. The plate was placed in a closed desiccator saturated with dry benzene and heated at 85° for 10-12 hr. The plate was freed from the solvent prior to development. The results are listed in Table 1.

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